

Petroleum ether-benzene (4 : 1) elution yielded olean-14 α ,15 α -oxido-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -ylacetate (2), m.p. 176–78°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1750 (acetoxy, carbomethoxy), 1270 (acetoxy) and 830 cm^{-1} (epoxide); δ_{H} (100 MHz; CDCl_3) 0.84–1.16 (21H, s, characteristic triterpenic methyl protons), 2.04 (3H, s, acetoxy), 3.20–3.28 (1H, d, $J \sim 6$ Hz, C_{15} -H), 3.68 (3H, s, carbomethoxy) and 4.40–4.56 (1H, m, $J \sim 6.5$ Hz, α -H at C_3); m/z 528 (M^+ , 93%), 510 ($M^+ - \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 20), 495 (5), 468 ($M^+ - 60$, 38), 408 ($M^+ - 60 - 60$, 12), 278 (52), 217 (45) and 189 (100%).

Further elution with benzene furnished olean-12-en-15 α -hydroxy-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl acetate (compound-A; 3), m.p. 190–92°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3540 (hydroxy), 1745 and 1250 (acetoxy), 1740 (carbomethoxy) and 830 cm^{-1} (olefinic double bond); δ_{H} (100 MHz; CDCl_3) 0.80–1.16 (21H, s, characteristic triterpenic methyl protons), 2.04 (3H, s, acetoxy), 2.76 and 2.88 (1H, dd, $J \sim 4$ Hz, C_{18} -H), 3.64 (3H, s, carbomethoxy), 4.04–4.20 (1H, m, methine proton at C_{15} bearing hydroxyl), 4.44–4.6 (1H, m, $J \sim 7$ Hz, α -H at C_3) and 5.36–5.44 (1H, m, $J \sim 4$ Hz, olefinic proton at C_{12}); m/z 528 (M^+ , 57%), 510 ($M^+ - \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 22), 468 ($M^+ - 60$, 61), 450 (15), 408 ($M^+ - 60 - 60$, 17), 278 (91), 249 (7), 219 (100) and 189 (33%).

Acetylation of compound-A (3): Acetic anhydride (2 ml) was added to a stirred solution of olean-12-en-15 α -hydroxy-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl-acetate (3; 0.3 g) in dry pyridine (2 ml). The mixture was allowed to warm slowly for 6 h and poured over crushed ice. Usual work up followed by purification by column chromatography and crystallisation yielded olean-12-en-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -15 α -diacetate (4), m.p. 210–12°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1720 (carbomethoxy), 1730, 1250 (acetoxy) and 830 cm^{-1} (olefinic double bond); δ_{H} (100 MHz; CDCl_3) 0.80–1.24 (characteristic triterpenic methyl protons), 2.0 and 2.04 (3H, s, two acetoxy groups), 2.76 and 2.88 (1H, dd, $J \sim 4$ Hz, C_{18} -H), 3.72 (3H, s, carbomethoxy), 4.44–4.6 (1H, m, $J \sim 6.5$ Hz, α -H at C_3) and 5.24–5.52 (2H, m, merged olefinic-H at C_{12} and C_{18} -H); m/z 570 (M^+ , 5), 510 ($M^+ - 60$, 59), 450 ($M^+ - 60 - 60$, 23), 390 ($M^+ - 60 - 60 - 60$, 15) and 189 (28).

BF_3 rearrangement of olean-14 α ,15 α -oxido-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl acetate (2): Olean-14 α ,15 α -oxido-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl-acetate (2; 0.2 g) was treated with BF_3 -etherate (0.2 ml) in dry benzene (20 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then neutralised with solid NaHCO_3 and washed with water till neutral. The organic layer was dried, filtered and evaporated to furnish a white solid (0.19 g) which upon chromatographic purification and subsequent crystallisation yielded a crystalline solid, m.p. 190–92°; it was found identical with olean-12-en-15 α -hydroxy-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl-acetate (3).

Dry HCl rearrangement of olean-14 α ,15 α -oxido-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl acetate (2): To a solution of olean-14 α ,15 α -oxido-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl acetate (0.2 g) in dry CHCl_3 (50 ml), dry HCl gas was passed

through for 3 h at room temperature. The CHCl_3 layer was then washed successively with NaHCO_3 and water and dried. The CHCl_3 layer was filtered and evaporated to furnish a white solid (0.18 g), which on chromatographic purification yielded a crystalline solid, m.p. 190–92°; it was found identical with olean-12-en-15 α -hydroxy-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -ylacetate (3).

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Synthesis of some Chalcones and their Antibacterial Activity

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SEVERAL workers^{1,2} synthesised chalcones and related compounds using alkyl as well as halogen substituted *o*-hydroxyacetophenones. Alkyl group present in *o*-hydroxyacetophenone enhances its activities due to its electron-releasing nature and facilitates the formation of chalcones. It was thought interesting to study the effect of alkyl groups when present in *meta*- and *para*-positions of phenolic group in the synthesis of chalcones and related compounds. Chalcones have been reported to possess various biological activities³.

2-Hydroxy-4,5-dimethylacetophenone (1) was condensed with substituted-benzaldehydes in presence of potassium hydroxide (40%) and the reaction was complete in 18 h. The chalcones were obtained in good yields. This may be due to the presence of methyl group in *para*-position to ketonic group. Methyl group in *meta*-position to ketonic group may have no effect on reactivity of ketone as observed by Marathey¹.

NOTES

The chalcones were brominated using 10% of bromine in acetic acid to yield α,β -dibromochalcones. The acetyl derivatives of chalcones were prepared using chalcone, acetic anhydride and pyridine. Melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R	Mol. formula	M p ** °C
2a	2-Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ Cl	94 ^a
b	4-Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ Cl	110 ^a
c	2,4-Cl ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ Cl ₂	126 ^a
d	4-CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂	81-82 ^b
e	2-OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₃	88 ^c
f	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄	104 ^c
g	3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₃	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₅	116 ^c
3a	2-Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ ClBr ₂	109 ^a
b	4-Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ ClBr ₂	118 ^a
c	2,4-Cl ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ Cl ₂ Br ₂	124 ^b
d	4-CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ Br ₂	138 ^a
e	2-OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₃ Br ₂	71 ^a
f	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄ Br ₂	78 ^b
g	3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₃	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₅ Br ₂	146-48 ^a
4a	2-Cl	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₃ Cl	92 ^b
b	4-Cl	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₃ Cl	96 ^b
c	2,4-Cl ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₃ Cl ₂	98 ^b
d	4-CH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₃	72 ^a
e	2-OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄	106 ^d
f	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₅	98 ^a
g	3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₆	106 ^a

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and halogen analyses

**Solvent for crystallisation: ^aC₆H₆, ^babsolute EtOH, ^cglacial AcOH, ^dMeOH

The paper disc method was used to test antibacterial activity of the chalcones against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. The inocula were obtained from agar solidified nutrient broth media and the growth was checked at 37° after 24 h and the zone of inhibition was measured.

As compared to chloramphenicol and 4,4'-sulphonyldianiline, the chalcones (2a-f) were found much less active against the representative strains of organisms; 2g was found comparatively most active.

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Syntheses of some 2-(2'-Methoxyphenyl)-chromones

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IN continuation of our investigation on chromones¹ we report here the synthesis of some 2-(2'-methoxyphenyl)chromones. These chromones have been obtained (Scheme 1) from the *o*-hydroxyacetophenones (1a-g).

The *o*-hydroxyacetophenone were converted to the respective *o*-benzoyloxy derivatives (2a-g) in good yield, by direct union of 1a-g with *o*-methoxybenzoic acid using POCl₃ as condensing agent². At higher temperature the yield decreased sharply. Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement of the esters (2a-g) gave the yellow β -diketones, but isolation of the diketones 3a-g could not be achieved as acidification with ice and dilute H₂SO₄ gave the chromones directly.

The structures of all the chromones were confirmed by elemental analyses and spectral data. An additional experimental confirmation was also achieved. A number of chromones, had earlier been brominated in our laboratory³ with the help of copper(II) bromide and the corresponding 3-bromo-